

Orchestration and Decentralized Governance in Permissioned Blockchains: A Systematic Mapping of Operational Approaches Supplementary Material

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Package reference and relation to the article

This document describes the contents of the Zenodo repository (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18616087>) associated with the article entitled *Orchestration and Decentralized Governance in Permissioned Blockchains: A Systematic Mapping of Operational Approaches*. The repository provides the artifacts that support the reproducibility and auditability of the study, including the protocol, source-specific search strings, import, deduplication, screening, and eligibility records, the QA checklist with justifications, and synthesis artifacts.

1 Package structure

The repository is organized according to the stages of the study, covering planning, search, selection, quality assessment, and synthesis. Table 1 presents its main components.

Table 1: Structure of the supplementary material repository (DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18616087>).

Component	Content
README.md	Description of the repository, its purpose, folder structure, and correspondence between the artifacts and the sections of the paper.
LICENSE	Repository license and note on third-party artifacts.
CITATION.cff	Citation metadata for this repository, including title, authors, version, and date.
CHANGELOG.md	Repository version history.
manifest-sha256.txt	Manifest with SHA-256 hashes of the repository files.
00-metadata/	Auxiliary deposit metadata, for example: <code>keywords.txt</code> , <code>related-identifiers.txt</code> , and <code>communities.txt</code> .
01-protocol/	Complete protocol in a readable and exportable format, covering PICOC (Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Context), RQs (research questions), QA (quality assessment), inclusion and exclusion criteria, and extraction and synthesis rules.
02-search-strings/	Original exports of source-specific results in BibTeX format (<code>.bib</code>) and representation of the canonical string.
03-raw-exports/	This version of the repository includes only README.md, which documents the expected contents and processing stage.
04-deduplication/	This version of the repository includes only README.md, which documents the expected contents and processing stage.
05-screening/	This version of the repository includes only README.md, which documents the expected contents and processing stage.
06-prisma/	Consolidated PRISMA counts, artifacts, and the flowchart figure in TikZ.
07-quality-assessment/	QA checklist applied to the included studies, with Y/P/N responses, scores, and item-by-item justifications.
08-data-extraction/	Study-level summary texts and operational fields, such as architecture, workflow, automation, and evidence, used in the synthesis.
09-synthesis/	Operational categories, evidence matrices, syntheses by RQ, and consolidated tables.
10-bibliography/	Bibliographic files, for example <code>.bib</code> , for the corpus and the references associated with the article.
11-data-analysis/	Aggregated figures derived from the consolidated record and the subset of included studies.

2 Mapping protocol

This section consolidates the protocol elements that guided planning, search, selection, and synthesis.

2.1 Scope

The scope covers operations and governance in permissioned blockchains, with a focus on: (i) orchestration and automation (IaC¹, DevOps², operators, and controllers), (ii) decentralized multi-organization governance, (iii) identity and access control, (iv) smart contract lifecycle, and (v) operational aspects of observability, security, resilience, and compliance.

2.2 PICOC

PICOC stands for Population, Intervention, Comparison, Outcome, and Context. In this mapping, the study does not operationalize Comparison or Outcome because it aims to map and characterize the literature rather than evaluate comparative effects.

P (Population): permissioned blockchains, for example, Hyperledger Fabric, Corda, Quorum, and Besu, and their operational components, such as nodes, channels, CAs, policies, and pipelines.

I (Intervention): orchestration and operational management solutions, including *operators/controllers*, management platforms, smart contract *lifecycle*, DevOps and IaC, observability, and resilience.

C (Context): multi-organization consortia, production environments, and industrial and academic proofs of concept, including regulated sectors.

2.3 Research questions

RQ1 What solutions exist for orchestration and operational management of permissioned blockchains?

¹Infrastructure as Code (IaC) is the practice of defining and provisioning infrastructure through code and versioned configurations, thereby automating the creation and modification of environments.

²DevOps is a set of practices that integrates development and operations to accelerate delivery through automation, continuous integration and delivery (CI/CD), monitoring, and reliability.

RQ1a: How do these solutions implement provisioning and automation? *RQ1b*: Which governance, identity, and access mechanisms do these solutions support?

RQ2 Which patterns and architectural approaches support provisioning, decentralized governance, identity and access management, and smart contract lifecycle?

RQ2a: How do solutions automate *deploy*, *upgrade*, and *rollback*?

RQ2b: How do APIs and *gateways* support discovery, routing, *caching*, and security?

RQ3 Which gaps and design implications emerge for open-source, *stack-agnostic* orchestration solutions?

RQ3a: Which requirements for observability, resilience, security, and compliance remain open? *RQ3b*: Which trade-offs arise from infrastructure and automation choices?

2.4 Search strategy

The study organizes the search strategy into three blocks: (i) *permissioned blockchains*, (ii) *orchestration/operations/provisioning/deployment/IaC/DevOps*, and (iii) *governance/multi-organization/policy/compliance/IAM*.

The repository records the canonical string, in its base form, as text and reproduces it in Appendix A.

2.5 Selection criteria

Inclusion (I1). Peer-reviewed primary studies *or* theses and dissertations (BDTD), published from 2020 onward, in Portuguese or English, with full text accessible and operational evidence, such as architecture, workflow, artifacts, or replicable details, for the orchestration and operational management of permissioned blockchains.

Exclusion (E1–E6). The exclusion criteria cover out-of-scope studies, studies focused only on the application or the contract, public DLT without a clearly defined permissioned counterpart, purely theoretical or cryptographic works without operational applicability, secondary studies (surveys, SLRs, or mappings), duplicates, superseded versions, language or year outside the scope, and unavailable full text.

2.6 Quality assessment (QA)

The QA checklist comprises 10 questions (QA1–QA10), with Y/P/N responses (1/0.5/0) and study-level justifications. Table 2 defines QA1–QA10, and Appendix H shows their application to the 23 included studies.

Table 2: Definitions of the quality checklist (QA1–QA10).

QA	Definition
QA1	The study addresses the orchestration and operational management of permissioned blockchains, including networks, consortia, channels, and infrastructure.
QA2	The study makes the permissioned platform or <i>stack</i> explicit or describes it with sufficient detail.
QA3	The study describes the solution architecture in terms of components, interfaces, and responsibilities.
QA4	The study makes the operational procedure explicit, including steps, workflow, automation, prerequisites, inputs, and outputs.
QA5	The study provides an implementation, a prototype, or sufficient detail for replication, such as scripts, IaC, configurations, or other artifacts.
QA6	The study addresses multi-organization governance concretely, considering consortium, channels, policies, roles, and decision-making.
QA7	The study addresses identity and access control concretely, including CA, permissions, and certificate lifecycle.
QA8	The study covers smart contract <i>lifecycle</i> , including <i>deploy</i> , <i>upgrade</i> , <i>rollback</i> , versioning, and policies.
QA9	The study addresses operational reliability, including observability, resilience, security, compliance, disaster recovery, and auditability.
QA10	The study presents evidence and evaluation, including metrics, experiments, case studies, comparisons, and limitations.

2.7 Extraction and synthesis

The study records extraction through study-level summary texts covering the problem, contribution, operational elements, evidence, and main gaps, guided by the RQs and the QA checklist. The synthesis organizes the evidence by operational categories, which are not mutually exclusive, and by research question (RQ1–RQ3).

3 PRISMA execution (consolidation)

The consolidated PRISMA counts are as follows:

- Records identified: 158 (7 sources).
- Duplicates removed: 27.

- Records screened (title and abstract): 131.
- Records excluded during screening: 108.
- Full texts assessed: 23.
- Full texts excluded at eligibility: 0.
- Studies included: 23.

Figure 1 reproduces the PRISMA flowchart in editable format (TikZ).

Figure 1: PRISMA flowchart of the selection process (editable version).

4 Quantitative analysis of the corpus

The directory `11-data-analysis/` contains three figures derived from the consolidated record in `articles(1).xls` and from the subset with status `Accepted`. These figures summarize the temporal distribution of the included studies and the distribution of the identified records and included studies by search source.

4.1 Distribution of records by source

The preserved search exports in `02-search-strings/` are in BibTeX format. Table 3 records the number of entries per file, obtained by counting occurrences of the `@` marker in the `.bib` files.

Table 3: Entries per BibTeX file in `02-search-strings/`.

File	Entries (n)
<code>ACMSearch.bib</code>	64
<code>BDTDSearch.bib</code>	4
<code>Engineering_VillageSearch.bib</code>	16
<code>ScienceDirectSearch.bib</code>	21
<code>ScienceDirect_citations_1765246633717.bib</code>	29
<code>ieeeSearch.bib</code>	27
<code>scopus_export_Dec8-2025_28cc1f04-61e3-4b94-8e8d-4aa999f53847.bib</code>	18

Note. The repository preserves two ScienceDirect export files. The paper uses the consolidated search results in the PRISMA counts, which yield 29 records.

4.2 Distribution of included studies by source

Based on the summary texts in `08-data-extraction/.article*_extract.txt`, Table 4 consolidates the number of included studies by search source.

Table 4: Included studies by search source (n=23).

Source	Included (n)
ACM Digital Library	9
Scopus (Elsevier)	5
IEEE Xplore	4
Engineering Village	3
ScienceDirect (Elsevier)	1
BDTD	1

4.3 Records identified by source (*Articles Per Source*)

Figure 2 presents the distribution of records identified in the search stage by source (*Articles Per Source*). According to the table displayed in Parsifal, the values are as follows: ACM Digital Library (64), ScienceDirect (29), IEEE Xplore (27), Scopus (18), Engineering Village (16), and BDTD (4), totaling $n=158$ records.

Figure 2: *Articles Per Source* (Parsifal): distribution of records identified in the search by source.

4.4 Selected versus accepted by source (*Accepted Articles Per Source*)

Figure 3 compares, for each source, the number of items marked in Parsifal as **Selected**, after screening and selection, and **Accepted**, corresponding to the final subset. In the Parsifal visualization, the accepted items total $n=23$, distributed by source as follows: ACM (9), Scopus (5), IEEE (4), Engineering Village (3), ScienceDirect (1), and BDTD (1).

Figure 3: *Accepted Articles Per Source* (Parsifal): comparison between *Selected* and *Accepted* items by source.

4.5 Temporal distribution in Parsifal (*Final Articles Per Year*)

Figure 4 shows *Final Articles Per Year (After study selection and quality assessment)*, that is, the annual count displayed by Parsifal for items considered “final” after the selection and QA stages. As indicated in the chart itself, the values by year are: 2020 (20), 2021 (30), 2022 (40), 2023 (60), 2024 (30), 2025 (40), and 2026 (10). This figure does not represent the distribution of the 23 accepted studies by year; rather, it represents the annual series displayed by Parsifal for “final articles.”

Figure 4: *Final Articles Per Year (Parsifal)*: annual count of “final” items after selection and QA, as exported from the system.

A Search strings and results by source

This appendix records the canonical string in its base form and identifies where the repository preserves the search artifacts.

A.1 Canonical string (base form) - text

The following text reproduces the complete canonical string, preserved in this supplement for direct consultation.

```

("permissioned blockchain" OR "permissioned blockchains" OR "permissioned blockchain network" OR
"permissioned blockchain networks" OR "permissioned BC" OR "permissioned BCs" OR "consortium blockchain"
OR "consortium blockchains" OR "enterprise blockchain" OR "enterprise blockchains" OR "private blockchain"
OR "private blockchains" OR "permissioned distributed ledger" OR "permissioned distributed ledgers" OR
"permissioned distributed ledger technology" OR "permissioned distributed ledger technologies" OR
"permissioned DLT" OR "consortium DLT")
AND
("orchestration" OR "orchestrations" OR "orchestrator" OR "orchestrators" OR "orchestrate" OR
"orchestrated" OR "orchestrating" OR "service orchestration" OR "network service orchestration" OR
"network services orchestration" OR "slice orchestration" OR "network slice orchestration" OR "cross-slice
communication" OR "cross slice communication" OR "service function chain" OR "service function chaining"
OR "SFC orchestration" OR "service function chain orchestration" OR "management and orchestration" OR
"management & orchestration" OR MANO OR "Network Functions Virtualization" OR "NFV-MANO" OR "NFV MANO" OR
"edge orchestrator" OR "multi domain edge orchestrator" OR "edge orchestration" OR "blockchain operation"
OR "blockchain operations" OR "blockchain service operations" OR "operations execution" OR "operations
execution method" OR "automatic deployment" OR "automated deployment" OR "blockchain deployment" OR
"deployment and management" OR "deployment framework" OR "workflow coordination" OR "workflow
orchestration" OR "blockchain management and monitoring platform" OR "blockchain management platform" OR
"System Operations for Permissioned Blockchain" OR "configuration and deployment" OR "setup and
configuration" OR "operation of a blockchain" OR "operation of a permissioned blockchain" OR "operating a
blockchain" OR "operating a permissioned blockchain" OR "load balancer" OR "container nodes")
AND
("governance" OR "network governance" OR "blockchain governance" OR "governance framework" OR "governance
model" OR "governance process" OR "governance processes" OR "peer-to-peer governance" OR "peer to peer
governance" OR "governance policy" OR "multi-stakeholder" OR "multi stakeholder" OR "multi-party" OR
"multi party" OR "multi-party business process" OR "multi party business process" OR "multi-domain" OR
"multi domain" OR "multi-domain environment" OR "multidomain" OR "multidomain environment" OR
"multi-cloud" OR "multi cloud" OR "multi-tenant" OR "multi tenant" OR "multi-operator" OR "multi operator"
OR "inter-operator" OR "inter operator" OR "cross-operator" OR "cross operator" OR "inter-operator
settlement" OR "inter operator settlement" OR "multi-organization" OR "multi organization" OR
"multi-organizational" OR "multi organisational" OR "multi-organisation" OR "multi organisation" OR
"inter-organizational" OR "inter organizational" OR "inter-organisational" OR "inter organisational" OR
"cross-organizational" OR "cross organizational" OR "cross-organisational" OR "cross organisational" OR
"crossinstitutional" OR "cross-institutional" OR "cross institutional" OR "trusted data transfer" OR
"trusted data-sharing" OR "trusted data sharing" OR "trusted resource sharing" OR "privilege separation"
OR "privilege-separated" OR "private data collection" OR "private data collections" OR "controlled
information sharing" OR "policy-based consensus" OR "policy based consensus" OR "multiple MANO systems" OR
"multiple NFV-MANO systems" OR "distributed NFV-MANO" OR "distributed NFV MANO" OR "multi-party business
processes" OR "multi party business processes" OR "multi-organizational network" OR "multi organizational
network" OR "multi-domain edge environment" OR "multi domain edge environment" OR "multi-domain edge
computing" OR "multi domain edge computing" OR "multi-domain services" OR "multi domain services" OR
"blockchain consortium" OR "multi-administrative domain" OR "multi administrative domain" OR "business
network" OR "business networks" OR "business group" OR "business groups" OR "trustless environment" OR
"group of organisations" OR "group of organizations" OR "management structures" OR "IT management
structures" OR "regulatory compliance" OR "decentralised framework" OR "decentralized framework" OR
"management and upscaling")

```

Figure 5: Complete search string.

A.2 Source-specific adaptations and result exports

The consolidated protocol in `01-protocol/systematic-mapping-complete-doc.docx.pdf` documents the syntax and field adaptations for each source. The repository stores the original result exports in BibTeX format in the `02-search-strings/*.bib` directory. It also stores the representation of the canonical string structure in `02-search-strings/search-string-figure.pdf`.

B List of included studies (metadata excerpt)

This appendix reproduces an excerpt from the summary texts in `08-data-extraction/.article*_extract.txt`, to facilitate traceability.

```
01 | Sato2021287 | 2021 | Scopus
02 | Sato20221318 | 2022 | Scopus
03 | 10.1145/3716324 | 2025 | ACM
04 | 9566184 | 2021 | IEEE
05 | 9933199 | 2022 | IEEE
06 | DELGADOVONEITZEN2026104038 | 2026 | ScienceDirect
07 | 10234371 | 2023 | IEEE
08 | 10.1145/3626641.3626673 | 2023 | ACM
09 | Silva2025102462 | 2025 | Scopus
10 | 9284604 | 2020 | IEEE
11 | Yu202461 | 2024 | Scopus
12 | Joseph2023748 | 2023 | Scopus
13 | TRAN2022103460 | 2022 | EV
14 | bruceproposiccao | 2023 | BDTD
15 | 10.1145/3724410 | 2025 | ACM
16 | 10.1145/3666013 | 2024 | ACM
17 | 10245496 | 2023 | EV
18 | 10.1145/3424771.3424796 | 2020 | ACM
19 | 10.1145/3643689 | 2024 | ACM
20 | 10.1145/3492323.3495633 | 2022 | ACM
21 | 10.1145/3462203.3475880 | 2021 | ACM
22 | 11114421 | 2025 | EV
23 | 10.1145/3564532 | 2023 | ACM
```

C BibTeX exports (signature excerpt)

This appendix reproduces, within the supplement itself, the initial signature, that is, type and key, of the first entry in each `.bib` file in `02-search-strings/`.

```
ACMSearch.bib: @inproceedings{10.1145/3631461.3631559,
BDTDSearch.bib: @mastersthesis{peter2021sotaru,
```

```
Engineering_VillageSearch.bib: @article{20232614308632 ,
ScienceDirectSearch.bib: @article{RAMOSCRUZ2024127427,
ScienceDirect_citations_1765246633717.bib: @article{XU2022105860,
ieeeSearch.bib: @ARTICLE{10148950,
scopus_export_Dec 8-2025_28cc1f04-61e3-4b94-8e8d-4aa999f53847.bib: @ARTICLE{Mishra2025,
```

D Corpus bibliography (representative excerpt)

The file 10-bibliography/corpus.bib contains 23 entries with status Accepted, generated from articles(1).xls. The following excerpt preserves the opening and the first entries as minimal internal content.

```
% corpus.bib
%
% Corpus bibliography (23 included studies)
% Metadata source: ../articles (1).xls (Articles sheet, status=Accepted)
%
@inproceedings{Sato2021287,
  author = {Sato, Tatsuya and Shimosawa, Taku and Himura, Yosuke},
  doi = {10.1109/Blockchain53845.2021.00046},
  note = {Source: Scopus (Elsevier)},
  pages = {287 - 294},
  title = {OpsSC: Decentralized Blockchain Network Operation Workflow for Hyperledger Fabric},
  year = {2021}
}

@article{Sato20221318,
  author = {Sato, Tatsuya and Shimosawa, Taku and Himura, Yosuke},
  doi = {10.1587/transcom.2021TMP0008},
  journal = {IEICE Transactions on Communications},
  pages = {1318 - 1331},
  title = {Operations Smart Contract to Realize Decentralized System Operations Workflow for Consortium Blockchain},
  year = {2022}
}
```

E Protocol (representative excerpt)

The directory 01-protocol/ contains the consolidated mapping protocol. The following excerpt replicates the minimum content recorded in 01-protocol/protocol.md.

```
# Systematic mapping protocol

The protocol, records, and evidence of the mapping were recorded in Parsifal
and consolidated in the files in this directory:

- ‘systematic-mapping-complete-doc.docx.pdf‘

This directory ‘01-protocol/‘ centralizes the consolidated record of the study.

Content covered by the consolidated protocol:
```

- PICOC (P/I/C)
- Research questions (RQ1-RQ3)
- Search strategy (canonical string and source-specific adaptations)
- Selection criteria (inclusion/exclusion)
- Quality checklist (QA1-QA10), definitions, and application
- Extraction/synthesis rules and artifacts

F Quality (representative excerpt)

The directory `07-quality-assessment/` consolidates the application of the QA checklist and the score for each study. The excerpts below replicate minimum content from `07-quality-assessment/qa-justifications.md` and `07-quality-assessment/qa-matrix.csv`.

```
# QA justifications
```

The item-by-item justifications (QA1-QA10) were recorded in Parsifal and consolidated in the document:

```
- '01-protocol/systematic-mapping-complete-doc.docx.pdf'
```

In this package, the consolidated matrix (Y/P/N and score) is in 'qa-matrix.csv'.

```
study_id,qa1,qa2,qa3,qa4,qa5,qa6,qa7,qa8,qa9,qa10,score
1,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,P,Y,P,Y,9.0
2,Y,Y,Y,Y,Y,P,Y,P,Y,9.0
3,P,Y,Y,Y,P,P,P,P,Y,8.0
4,Y,Y,P,Y,Y,P,P,P,P,7.5
5,Y,Y,Y,Y,N,P,P,P,Y,7.5
```

G Extraction by study (representative excerpt)

The directory `08-data-extraction/` preserves one summary text for each included study. The excerpt below replicates the beginning of `08-data-extraction/.article1_extract.txt`.

```
Study 01
BibTeX key: Sato2021287
```

```
Title: OpsSC: Decentralized Blockchain Network Operation Workflow for Hyperledger Fabric
Authors: Sato, Tatsuya and Shimosawa, Taku and Himura, Yosuke
Year: 2021
Type: Conference paper
Source: Scopus (Elsevier)
DOI: 10.1109/Blockchain53845.2021.00046
URL: https://www.scopus.com/inward/record.uri?eid=2-s2.0-85125677245&...
```

```
Study synthesis and operational evidence
```

It proposes and implements an orchestration/operational automation solution for a permissioned blockchains (Hyperledger Fabric v2.x) focused on inter-organizational operations; it covers multi-org governance through proposal + voting and automates the end-to-end workflow of channels and chaincode lifecycle (deploy/upgrade/commit), including REST API + agents and on-chain logging/auditability.

H Quality assessment - QA matrix (23 studies)

This appendix replicates the QA matrix (QA1–QA10) applied to the 23 included studies.

Table 5: Quality checklist applied to the included studies (QA1–QA10). Y=Yes, P=Partial, N=No.

<i>Study</i>	<i>QA1</i>	<i>QA2</i>	<i>QA3</i>	<i>QA4</i>	<i>QA5</i>	<i>QA6</i>	<i>QA7</i>	<i>QA8</i>	<i>QA9</i>	<i>QA10</i>	<i>Points</i>
1 [Sato et al. 2021]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P	Y	9.0
2 [Sato et al. 2022]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P	Y	9.0
3 [Hawashin et al. 2025]	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	Y	P	P	Y	8.0
4 [Hoiss et al. 2021]	Y	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	7.5
5 [Kassab et al. 2022]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P	P	Y	7.5
6 [von Eitzen et al. 2026]	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P	P	Y	7.0
7 [Marathe et al. 2023]	P	Y	Y	Y	Y	P	P	N	P	Y	7.0
8 [Putri et al. 2023]	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	N	P	P	P	6.5
9 [Silva et al. 2025]	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	P	P	P	6.5
10 [Rondanini et al. 2020]	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	P	P	P	Y	6.5
11 [Yu et al. 2024]	Y	Y	P	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	N	6.5
12 [Joseph et al. 2023]	P	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	N	Y	Y	6.5
13 [Tran et al. 2022]	Y	P	Y	Y	Y	P	N	N	P	Y	6.5
14 [Bruce 2022]	P	Y	Y	Y	P	P	P	N	P	Y	6.5
15 [Bandara et al. 2025]	P	Y	P	Y	P	P	P	N	P	Y	6.0
16 [Loghin et al. 2024]	P	Y	P	P	Y	P	P	N	P	Y	6.0
17 [Mathwale 2023]	Y	Y	P	P	Y	N	P	P	P	P	6.0
18 [Bandara et al. 2020]	P	N	Y	Y	P	P	P	P	P	P	5.5
19 [Belchior et al. 2024]	P	P	Y	Y	P	P	P	N	P	N	5.0
20 [Kashansky et al. 2022]	P	Y	Y	P	P	N	N	N	P	P	4.5
21 [Kashansky et al. 2021]	P	Y	P	N	P	P	P	N	P	P	4.5
22 [Sato et al. 2025]	Y	Y	P	P	N	P	N	N	P	N	4.0
23 [Belchior et al. 2023]	N	P	Y	P	N	P	N	N	P	P	3.5

I Log files and spreadsheets (fields and conventions)

The directories 03-raw-exports/, 04-deduplication/, 05-screening/, and 07-quality-assessment/ include spreadsheets and tables in formats such as .csv and .xlsx. Taken together, these files preserve:

- record identifier by source and deduplication key;
- screening decision, with inclusion or exclusion, and reason for exclusion;

- full-text eligibility decision;
- QA1–QA10 responses, score, and item-by-item justifications.

How to cite

Cite this repository using the Zenodo DOI <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18616087>.
Citation metadata are also available in `CITATION.cff`.

References

- [Bandara et al. 2025] Bandara, H. D., Staples, M., and Malik, S. (2025). Designing for shared ledgers in industry ecosystems.
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- [Hoiss et al. 2021] Hoiss, T., Seidenfad, K., and Lechner, U. (2021). Blockchain service operations - a structured approach to operate a blockchain solution. pages 11–19.
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